

CHARACTERIZING THE MECHANICAL RESPONSE OF CORNEA USING BIAXIAL TESTS

M.E Emu, H. Hatami-Marbini

Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, University of Illinois at Chicago, Chicago, Illinois, USA,
Email. hatami@uic.edu

INTRODUCTION

The cornea is a transparent tissue that covers the front of the eye and has unique mechanical properties. The cornea and sclera protect internal parts of the eye globe, i.e., iris, pupil, and lens. The cornea is a tissue that is exposed to the outside environment; thus, it could undergo significant amount of external pressure that is, for example, caused by eye rubbing and sudden injuries. The cornea is composed of five layers, i.e. epithelium, Bowman's layer, stroma, Descemet's membrane, and endothelium. The stroma is its thickest layer and comprises about 90 percent of the corneal thickness. The corneal stroma is mainly composed of water, collagen fibers, and proteoglycans that are found in the form of many superimposed lamellae. The uniform diameter and regular arrangement of collagen fibers in the corneal stroma are essential for its transparency and unique optical properties. In addition, the stromal layer is responsible for the structural properties of the cornea.

The mechanical behavior of the cornea has been mainly investigated using the in vitro uniaxial tensile testing method and inflation method [1-3]. In the tensile experiments, uniaxial tensile force or displacement is applied to cornea strips for investigating their stress-strain behavior. In the inflation testing method, the deformation of corneal samples subjected to posterior pressure is determined. These testing techniques showed that the cornea has a rate-dependent and anisotropic mechanical behavior. However, the exact relationship

between the corneal microstructure and anisotropic mechanical properties has not yet been fully characterized. The ability to understand and predict anisotropic corneal response is of significant importance for developing a proper material model that is able to accurately capture the corneal mechanical response. The biaxial tensile test is an experimental testing method that has been used to characterize the mechanical properties of biological tissues; however, it has not been commonly employed to investigate corneal biomechanics. The biaxial testing is particularly useful for characterizing the mechanical response of anisotropic materials, i.e. it could determine the influence of collagen fiber orientation on the mechanical response of a material. It is known that collagen fibers in the healthy human cornea have two preferred orientations orthogonal to each other, i.e. they are primarily in the horizontal (nasal-temporal) and vertical (inferior-superior) directions. The primary objective of the present work was to conduct biaxial tensile experiments to determine the anisotropic biomechanical response of the corneal samples.

METHODS

Five porcine eyes were brought to the laboratory and corneal rings with sclera were dissected carefully from the eyeballs. A square sample was then prepared from the center part of each cornea-scleral ring. The samples were allowed to air-dry or were allowed to swell in solution until their thickness was about 800 μm . A pachymeter (DGH Technology Inc., Pennsylvania) was used to measure the thickness of

specimens. The samples were mounted into the planar biaxial machine (ElectroForce TestBench), Figure 1. The samples were stretched along the nasal-temporal (NT) and superior-inferior (SI) directions at a stretch ratio of 1:1 with a displacement rate of 2 mm/min. A tare force was initially applied to remove slack, and ensure the firm grip of samples, and have a complete contact with the specimens. The samples were then strained up equally in each direction. The stress was defined as the measured force divided by the initial cross-sectional area of the samples in order to determine the stress-strain curves. The data was reported as mean \pm standard deviation and one-way ANOVA with a significance level of 0.05 was used for the statistical analysis.

Figure 1: The corneal specimens were gripped into the planar biaxial machine such that nasal-temporal (NT) and superior-inferior (SI) directions were aligned in the vertical and horizontal axes, respectively.

RESULTS

The experimental stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 2. From the stress-strain curves, the elastic modulus at 6% strain was calculated. The mean maximum stress was 0.09 MPa and 0.07 MPa in NT and SI directions, respectively. The variation in the maximum stress of NT and SI directions was statistically significant but the variation in the elastic modulus was not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

The primary purpose of this study was to characterize the anisotropic mechanical response of porcine cornea using the biaxial tensile testing method. A different nonlinear stress-strain curve was observed for each direction (Fig. 2). The collagen fibril orientations and arrangements inside the corneal stroma are responsible for the observed variation in tensile stress-strain curves.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curve of porcine corneal samples obtained from the biaxial experiments. The symbols show the average response and the error bars indicate one standard deviation.

Previous imaging studies have shown a clear preferential orientation of collagen fibrils in the vertical and horizontal directions [4-5]. The mechanical measurements of the present study can be used along with these imaging results to relate the macroscopic response of the cornea in terms of its microstructure. The biaxial testing has a number of limitations. For example, the specimens were initially curved and they had variable thickness. The number of samples used in the present study was also small and future experiments are undergoing in our laboratory to decrease the variability in the measurements. Despite these limitations, the present work showed that biaxial experiments could be used to characterize the nonlinear anisotropic mechanical response of the corneal samples.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported in part by grants from the National Science Foundation (1636659) and the National Institutes of Health (R21 EY030264).

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Elsheikh, K. Anderson. Comparative study of corneal strip extensometry and inflation tests *Journal of Royal Society – Interface* 2, 177-185, 2005.
- [2] B. Boyce, J. Grazier, R. Jones, D. Nguyen. Full-field deformation of bovine cornea under constrained inflation conditions. *Biomaterials*. 29. 3896-904, 2004.
- [3] H. Hatami-Marbini, and A. Rahimi. Interrelation of hydration, collagen cross-linking treatment, and biomechanical properties of the cornea. *Current eye research* 41.5, 616-622, 2016
- [4] K.M. Meek, T. Blamires, G.F. Elliot, T.J. Gyi, C. Nave, The organization of collagen fibrils in the human corneal stroma: a synchrotron x-ray diffraction study. *Current Eye Research*, 6:841-846, 1987
- [5] K.M. Meek, R.H. Newton, Organization of collagen fibrils in the corneal stroma in relation to mechanical properties and surgical practice. *Journal of Refractive Surgery*, 15(6):695-699, 1999.